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Lead Beneficiary	<i>University of Toulouse</i>
Authors	A.P. Rouillard, N. Wijsen, M. Jarry, A. Papaioannou, N. Talebpour, & J. Gieseler

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List of Acronyms

ACE	Advanced Composition Explorer
CCMC	Community Coordinated Modelling Center
GCS	Graduated Cylindrical Shell
CME	Coronal Mass Ejection
DONKI	The Space Weather Database Of Notifications, Knowledge, Information
ESP	Energetic Storm Particle
EFR3D	3-D Eruptive Flux Rope Model
EUHFORIA	European heliospheric forecasting information asset
Fri3D	Flux Rope in 3D
GCR	Galactic Cosmic Ray
HelioCast	Heliospheric Forecasting Model
PARADISE	PArticle RADIation Asset Directed at Interplanetary Space Exploration
GLE	Ground Level Enhancement
LASCO	Large Angle and Spectrometric Coronagraph Experiment
MO	Magnetic Obstacles
MAST	Magneto-hydrodynamic Algorithm outside a Sphere
MFR	Magnetic Flux Rope
MFRs	Magnetic Flux Ropes
MHD	MagnetoHydroDynamic
SEP	Solar Energetic Particle
SOHO	Solar and Heliospheric Observatory
SQ	Science Question
STEREO	Solar-Terrestrial Relations Observatory
SPEARHEAD	SPEcification, Analysis & Re-calibration of High Energy pArticle Data
WP	Work Package
UPS	Université Toulouse III-Paul Sabatier
WISPR	Wide Imager of PSP

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The primary driver of shock waves in the solar corona and the interplanetary medium is a fast Magnetic Flux Rope (MFR), which forms the core structure of most Coronal Mass Ejection (CME)s. A MFR consists of helical magnetic field lines wrapped around a central axis and characterised by strong magnetic pressure. Because this structure is typically out of equilibrium with the surrounding plasma, it undergoes substantial three-dimensional expansion during its outward propagation. The propagation of MFRs significantly modifies the structure of the interplanetary medium, which can therefore no longer be approximated as a simple Parker spiral. These evolving magnetic configurations strongly influence the transport of Solar Energetic Particle (SEP)s. During periods of high solar activity, SEPs accelerated close to the Sun are unlikely to propagate to 1 AU along an undisturbed Parker spiral. Instead, they travel through magnetic perturbations — including MFRs — generated by preceding solar eruptions. Rouillard et al. (2016) showed that most Ground Level Enhancement (GLE) events occur during intervals of very high solar activity, when accelerated particles propagate through well-defined MFRs or more complex magnetic structures. Transport through MFRs is expected to substantially modify the path length, diffusion processes, spatial extent, and spectral properties of SEPs. In addition to their role in particle transport, MFRs are also central to the occurrence of Forbush decreases, which result from the modulation of Galactic Cosmic Rays (GCRs) by the enhanced magnetic fields and plasma structures associated with CMEs. The strong magnetic fields and turbulent sheath regions preceding MFRs reduce the diffusion of GCRs, leading to the characteristic rapid decrease and gradual recovery observed in energetic particle data. The present deliverable, led by Université Toulouse III-Paul Sabatier (UPS), presents the results of modelling the propagation of MFRs and assessing their impact on energetic particle transport. This work exploits several techniques to model and propagate magnetic flux ropes to 1 AU. Within this task, we developed a new modelling framework to investigate the influence of MFRs on SEP transport, applying it to SPEcification, Analysis & Re-calibration of High Energy pArticle Data (SPEARHEAD)'s case studies of recent GLE events in 2024.

1 Introduction

3-D modelling of a Magnetic Flux Rope (MFR) at the core of Coronal Mass Ejections (CMEs) observed in coronal imagery and measured in-situ can be carried out by fitting semi-analytical models of MFRs or running full 3-D MagnetoHydroDynamic (MHD) models of CME formation and/or expansion. Semi-analytical approaches typically rely on flux-rope geometries constrained by remote-sensing observations and in-situ magnetic field measurements, allowing the derivation of key parameters such as orientation, size, magnetic field strength, and helicity. In contrast, full 3-D MHD simulations self-consistently describe the initiation and propagation of CMEs within a structured solar wind background, capturing the dynamical evolution of the embedded MFR and its interaction with the ambient interplanetary medium. Both approaches were used in the present deliverable. This combined strategy enables cross-validation between observationally constrained fits and physics-based numerical modelling, thereby increasing the robustness of the inferred MFR properties. Similar to the shock modelling carried out in D4.3 (Rouillard et al. 2025), a full 3-D fitting of a MFR based on coronal imagery can only be done after 2006 when the Solar-Terrestrial Relations Observatory (STEREO) spacecraft were launched and provided at least a second viewpoint to base our CME triangulation on. The availability of multiple vantage points significantly reduces projection effects and improves the determination of the three-dimensional morphology, propagation direction, and expansion properties of the erupting structure.

The main goal of the MFR fitting is to support the analysis of Forbush decreases reported in D5.3 (Dumbovic et al. 2025), as well as to provide a tool for studying the transport of Solar Energetic Particle (SEP)s through complex interplanetary conditions. In particular, characterising the magnetic topology and large-scale structure of MFRs is essential for understanding how they modulate Galactic Cosmic Rays (GCRs) and how they influence the access, confinement, and scattering of energetic particles. Considering these goals, the focus was therefore put on the interplanetary component of the MFR and its associated in-situ signature. This includes the detailed examination of magnetic field rotations, plasma parameters, bidirectional electron signatures, and other indicators commonly used to identify MFRs in spacecraft data. In this deliverable D4.4 (Rouillard et al. 2026), we focused on the analysis of high priority events presented in D4.1 (Rouillard et al. 2024) that were associated with significant Forbush decreases and/or cases of SEP transport through MFRs. The selected events were chosen based on their intensity, data availability, and relevance for linking remote-sensing observations with in-situ measurements, ensuring a consistent multi-instrument and multi-spacecraft analysis whenever possible.

The next deliverable D4.5 (due M32) will focus on a systematic analysis of the state of the interplanetary medium measured in-situ during the major SEPs considered in SPEcification, Analysis & Re-calibration of High Energy pArticle Data (SPEARHEAD). This effort will extend the event-based approach adopted in Rouillard et al. (2026) to a statistically significant sample, enabling a more comprehensive assessment of the role played by large-scale interplanetary structures in shaping high-energy particle events. That deliverable will provide a comprehensive catalogue documenting the presence or absence of MFRs during all SEP events with energies > 100 MeV (Jarry et al. 2026). In addition, relevant parameters such as magnetic field strength, flux-rope orientation, radial distance, and the relative timing between SEP onset and MFR passage will be systematically compiled to facilitate future comparative and modelling studies.

In the present deliverable D4.4, we modelled MFRs through two approaches:

- *Sub-task 4.4.1:* Semi-analytical modelling was applied to flux ropes associated with significant Forbush decreases. The CME events analysed include the 12 July 2012 and the 3 April 2010 ones, both of which were linked to strong Forbush decreases. In addition, in the course of establishing this framework, we also investigated the very recent event of 19 January 2026, which produced the

most intense low-energy Energetic Storm Particle (ESP) radiation storm observed since 1974 and was accompanied by a substantial Forbush decrease.

- *Sub-task 4.4.2:* Full 3-D modelling of flux ropes was performed for key events identified in D4.1 that were associated with Ground Level Enhancements (GLEs) occurring during the in-situ passage of flux ropes. In addition to reconstructing the large-scale magnetic structure of these events, we assessed the influence of the flux ropes on the propagation/transport of SEPs from the Sun to Earth. The events considered in this analysis are GLE71 and GLE74 (Papaioannou et al. 2025).

2 Modelling Magnetic Flux ropes

When CMEs propagate outward from the Sun, they experience substantial expansion driven by their strong internal magnetic pressure and the rapid decrease of the ambient solar wind pressure with heliocentric distance. This expansion occurs both radially, along the direction of propagation, and laterally, perpendicular to it, leading to a progressive increase in the size of the embedded MFR. As a result, the cross-sectional area of the flux rope grows with distance, and its magnetic field strength typically decreases due to conservation of magnetic flux and expansion-related dilution. This global expansion can significantly increase the longitudinal and latitudinal extent of the structure, thereby enhancing its probability of intersecting planetary environments or spacecraft located far from the eruption's initial trajectory. The MFR itself is a coherent, twisted bundle of magnetic field lines organised around a central axis. Its evolution is largely governed by the interplay between magnetic pressure, magnetic tension, and the forces exerted by the surrounding plasma. A quasi-steady MFR configuration can be maintained when a dynamic balance is achieved between the outward magnetic pressure, the restoring magnetic tension of the helical field lines, the external thermal and dynamic pressure of the solar wind, and dissipative processes occurring at its boundaries. Although the overall expansion is continuous, local equilibrium conditions may temporarily stabilise the large-scale structure during its interplanetary propagation.

When MFRs propagate faster than the ambient solar wind, their leading edge and flanks become compressed, resulting in enhanced magnetic field strength, plasma density, and electric current densities at the flux-rope boundary. This compression modifies the local plasma beta and can alter the stability of the boundary layers. The interaction between the outward-moving CME MFR and the background solar wind may drive the formation of a shock (see D4.3; Rouillard et al. 2025) if the relative speed exceeds the local fast magnetosonic speed. Between the shock and the flux rope, a turbulent and compressed region develops, commonly referred to as the “sheath”. This sheath region is characterised by strong magnetic fluctuations, enhanced plasma temperature, and disturbed flow velocities, and it plays a crucial role in modulating galactic cosmic rays and influencing SEP transport. Capturing these compressive and non-linear processes requires full 3-D MHD modelling, as simplified analytical approaches cannot self-consistently reproduce shock formation, sheath dynamics, and large-scale solar wind interactions.

In addition to large-scale expansion and compression effects, non-linear magnetic forces and reconnection processes occurring in the trailing current sheet can further modify the topology of the MFR. Magnetic reconnection may lead to flux erosion, restructuring of field-line connectivity, or the detachment of portions of the flux rope. Despite the largely collisionless nature of the coronal and interplanetary plasma, sharp current layers can develop at the surface of the MFR due to strong gradients in magnetic field, plasma density, temperature, and bulk flow velocity. Across these boundary layers, non-ideal and dissipative processes — such as anomalous resistivity, kinetic-scale diffusion, and wave–particle interactions — may become important, enabling magnetic flux evolution, partial erosion of the flux rope, plasma heating, or particle acceleration. These localised and inherently complex microphysical processes operate on spatial and temporal scales that are not resolved by the global modelling framework adopted in the present deliverable. Consequently, the modelling presented here focuses on the large-scale properties,

global expansion, and heliospheric evolution of the **MFR**, while smaller-scale kinetic and boundary-layer effects remain beyond its scope.

Three-dimensional reconstruction of **CME MFR** structures requires simultaneous coronal imaging from multiple vantage points in order to accurately constrain their geometry, orientation, kinematics, and temporal evolution. Single-viewpoint observations suffer from strong projection effects, making it difficult to distinguish between intrinsic structural properties and line-of-sight ambiguities. Routine multi-perspective observations only became available after the 2006 launch of the **STEREO** mission, which, together with near-Earth observatories, provided the additional lines of sight necessary for reliable flux-rope triangulation. The stereoscopic capability enabled more accurate determination of the **CME** propagation direction, angular width, axis orientation, cross-sectional shape, and magnetic twist, significantly improving our ability to connect remote-sensing observations with in-situ measurements at 1 AU.

Accurate 3-D **MFR** fitting is a complex and largely manual procedure that requires careful visual inspection and iterative adjustment of model geometries to coronagraph and heliospheric imager data. Commonly used geometrical representations include ellipsoidal shells, croissant- or torus-shaped flux ropes, and Graduated Cylindrical Shell (**GCS**) models. These geometries must be consistently aligned with successive images from multiple spacecraft while accounting for temporal evolution, expansion, and projection effects. Small changes in viewing angle or assumed model parameters can significantly affect the inferred orientation and size of the **MFR**, making the fitting process highly sensitive and demanding rigorous scrutiny. As a result, this procedure is inherently time-consuming and requires expert judgement to ensure physically consistent solutions.

Given these practical constraints, comprehensive 3-D **MFR** reconstruction could only be performed for a limited number of high-priority events. The selection criteria prioritised events associated with significant Forbush decreases, strong **SEPs** and/or **GLEs**, where an accurate characterisation of the large-scale magnetic structure is essential for interpreting particle transport and cosmic-ray modulation. Deliverable 4.4 (D4.4; [Rouillard et al. 2026](#)), therefore focuses on providing detailed **MFR** modelling for selected key events, with the dual objective of supporting the analysis of **SEP** propagation through complex heliospheric magnetic configurations and improving the physical interpretation of associated Forbush decreases. By combining stereoscopic reconstruction with in-situ flux-rope fitting and global modelling, this work establishes a consistent framework linking coronal evolution, interplanetary structure, and energetic particle observations.

2.1 Semi-Analytical modelling of MFRs with the 3-D Eruptive Flux Rope Model (**EFR3D**)

2.1.1 General context of **MFR** modelling

The advent of coronal and solar wind imaging from multiple vantage points, thanks to the **STEREO** spacecraft, revolutionized the monitoring and modelling of **CMEs MFRs**. The continuous tracking of large **CMEs** from the Sun to spacecraft (observer) has provided critical information on how **MFRs** expand/contract, rotate, and deflect in 3-D from the Sun to 1 AU. For the fast **CMEs**, the contour of the shock-sheath region that surrounds the **MFR** can also be used to infer the 3-D topology of the shock from the corona to the interplanetary medium as we saw and exploited in D4.3 ([Rouillard et al. 2025](#)). White-light imagery, and heliospheric imagery in particular, thus provides crucial information on the global 3-D substructures of the **CME**. Unfortunately, total brightness images cannot be used to measure the properties of the magnetic field transported by **CMEs**. However, the distribution of that magnetic field, and of the associated currents inside and around the **MFR**, influence the internal structure and kinematic properties of **CMEs** that we seek to analyse here.

Figure 1: Frontal view of a **MFR** coming towards the observer. The internal magnetic topology of the **EFR3D** model is shown here. The red line traces the poloidal magnetic field component of the **MFR** while the blue line corresponds to the toroidal component. The green line is an intermediate component mixing poloidal and toroidal fields.

The multipoint *STEREO* mission has definitely validated the croissant-shaped structure of **MFRs** for at least a subset of **CMEs**, with an occasional good correspondence found between **MFR** orientations inferred in simultaneous in-situ measurements and white-light imaging (Rouillard et al. 2020). This important step has fundamental implications for our understanding of the dynamic evolution of this subset of **CMEs**. A new generation of **MFR** fitting models includes non-force-free assumptions, as well as significant deformation of the internal structure as the **MFR** propagates in the interplanetary medium (Isavnin 2016; Rouillard et al. 2020). In the present deliverable we make use of the **EFR3D** model detailed in Rouillard et al. (2020) and summarised below, as well as the Fried-3D model of Isavnin (2016).

2.1.2 The EFR3D model

The **EFR3D** model consists of different modules that can be used to fit coronal and heliospheric observations of **MFR** as well as solve the physics of the evolution of the internal magnetic field. The internal part of a flux rope is shown in Figure 1 with the toroidal/intermediate and poloidal components of the **MFR** shown in blue, green and red, respectively.

Figure 2 presents the 3-D shape of the **CME** boundary assumed in this paper to model the **CME** observed by the Large Angle and Spectrometric Coronagraph Experiment (**LASCO**) and Wide Imager of (**WISPR**) instruments. The **MFR** is a bent toroid with a constant major radius, R , but a varying minor radius, a with azimuthal angle (φ). The legs of the **MFR** remain attached to the Sun and have a much smaller cross section at the Sun than the apex of the **MFR**. A constant R means that the **MFR** has a circular symmetry (Figure 2). This “circular current channel” is used to calculate the forces acting on such an **MFR** when it erupts in the solar corona (Rouillard et al. 2020). Past studies have found evidence that **MFRs** with non-circular current channels can also successfully fit the aspect of **CMEs** in coronagraph images taken from different vantage points. In addition, the forces acting on elliptically shaped current channels have also been quantified for ideal cases. We defer the analysis of these more complex geometries to a future study. In addition to the circularity of the current channel, past studies also assumed that the toroid’s minor radius increased either exponentially or linearly with azimuthal angle (φ) from the footpoints to the apex of the **MFR**. This simplifies the calculation of the inductance of the system, an important step to calculate the forces acting on the **MFR**. These past formulations for the minor radius were justified in the 1D calculation of an **MFR** force balance but cannot be used to produce a 3-D representation of the **MFR**. These variations in $a(\varphi)$ lead to discontinuities in the magnetic flux surfaces of the **MFR** near its apex and prevent a 3-D mapping of the internal magnetic field lines.

Figure 2: The MFR geometry assumed in the EFR3D model viewed from solar north (top) and from the side (bottom). The different dimensions of the toroidal structure used in Equation 1 are also labeled.

To obtain a more adequate 3-D topology, the present study assumes a bell curve for the variation of the minor radius $a(\varphi)$ with azimuthal angle (φ) measured between the footpoint and the apex:

$$a(\varphi) = a_a \exp \left[- \left(\frac{\varphi}{\varphi_f} \right)^2 \ln \left(\frac{a_a}{a_f} \right) \right] \quad (1)$$

where a_f and a_a are the minor radii at the footpoint and apex, and φ_f is azimuthal angle at the footpoint of the MFR. We have retained here a notation similar to that of Chen (1996), to ease comparison of the different assumed geometries. The minor radius of the MFR varies slowly near the apex, with only a 10% variation of the minor radius along a quarter of the torus centred at the apex. As we shall see, this slowly varying minor radius near the apex of the torus is more consistent with the assumptions made to analytically derive the Lorentz forces acting on the system.

2.1.3 Exploiting EFR3D model for (Rouillard et al. 2026)

We assume this same MFR shape to model the CME evolution in 3-D, and to compute the forces acting on the CME during its eruption process. We will not detail the physics of the EFR3D model here which can be found in the paper by Rouillard et al. (2020) but instead provide some of the general features of the technique.

As an illustration, we show in Figure 3 a comparison of the EFR3D model with white-light observations taken by the STEREO and near-Earth spacecraft of the 12 July 2012 CME event (one of the priority

Figure 3: Sequence of white-light images of the Earth impacting CME of 12 July 2012 taken by STEREO-A (left), SOHO (middle) and STEREO-B (right). Overlaid on each image are shown in blue the output of the EFR3D model.

events listed in Rouillard et al. (2024) and analysed as part of Rouillard et al. (2026)). This latter event caused a strong SEP event as well as a significant Forbush decrease of GCRs measured at Earth by neutron monitors. The surface of the modelled MFR is compared to the outline of the 12 July 2012 CME event imaged by coronagraph and heliospheric imagers in order to locate approximately the MFR in 3-D space. The main difficulty in making such fits is related to the localisation of the MFR especially when strong sheath/shock regions are present around the eruptive flux rope.

The accuracy of the imagery-based shock fitting procedure depends on: (1) the general availability of simultaneous observations from at least two viewpoints, (2) the overall cadence of the imaging, (3) the existence of previous events and the overall contamination of images (by high energy particles), and (4) the separation angle of the viewpoints with respect to the source region. That is why we generally stop the fitting at 20-25 solar radii.

The magnetic field modelled by the EFR3D model can be extracted at specific points of interest in the heliosphere and compared to in-situ data. Figure 4 shows a comparison of the modelled MFR with measurements taken by the Advanced Composition Explorer (ACE) and Wind spacecraft at L1 at the time of impact of the CME of the 12 July 2012.

To support the research on Forbush decreases to be carried as part of the upcoming Deliverable D5.4

Figure 4: Comparison between in-situ measurements of the [EFR3D](#) model (solid lines) and the in-situ measurements of the solar wind plasma by the Wind spacecraft at the time of impact of the CME (dotted lines).

(currently in progress), we modelled in this same way the Earth-impacting [CME](#) of 03 April 2010 as well as the very recent 19 January 2026 [CME](#) event (on-going analysis) that caused both the strongest [ESP](#) radiation storm since 1974 and a very strong Forbush decrease. To study particle transport processes through [MFR](#), we also fitted the events of [GLE71](#) and [GLE74](#). For these events, advanced 3-D MHD modelling of the flux ropes was also carried out and is presented in section 3.

2.1.4 The Flux Rope in 3D ([Fri3D](#)) model

The other semi-analytical [MFR](#) model used in this deliverable was the [Fri3D](#) model ([Isavnin 2016](#)). This model accounts for the [CME](#)'s overall geometry, accounting for major distortions, including deflection, rotation, expansion, pancaking, front flattening, and rotational skew. [Fri3D](#) embeds a 3-D flux-rope magnetic geometry: collections of helical field lines tied at both solar footpoints forming a croissant-shaped structure; field lines are constructed from parallel lines in a unit-radius cylinder whose length equals the model axis length L and a constant low twist τ (chirality ± 1) makes them spiral gently from footpoint to footpoint; the radial (poloidal) field profile follows a Lundquist-like solution across the cross-section ([Isavnin 2016](#)). The [CME](#)'s analytical three-dimensional magnetic structure was shown in past studies to replicate in-situ magnetic field observations for spacecraft encounters of any complexity ([Isavnin 2016](#)). This model was used in conjunction with full 3-D MHD to simulate the outward propagation of the Magnetic Flux Ropes ([MFRs](#)) through which the [SEPs](#) propagated during [GLE71](#) and [GLE74](#) (described in the next section).

3 3-D MHD modelling [MFRs](#):

[GLEs](#) occur frequently during high levels of solar activity when the interplanetary medium is disturbed by [CME](#) propagating to 1 AU ([Rouillard et al. 2016](#)). To reach Earth-like distances, these very energetic particles often propagate through complex interplanetary magnetic fields. Such conditions were met during

the geomagnetic superstorm of May 2024.

Figure 5: Illustration of the full modelling set-up put in place by WP4 in order to support the catalogue exploitation and science analysis carried out in WP5. In this illustration we see the shock modelling achieved in D4.3; Rouillard et al. (2025), the modelling of the preceding CME and its MFR (D4.4; Rouillard et al. 2026) through which the accelerated SEPs have to propagate to reach 1 AU.

3.1 Building new 3-D MHD MFR modelling pipelines:

In order to address one of the Science Questions (SQs) of the SPEARHEAD project which was to study the transport properties of SEPs between the acceleration region in the solar corona and their detection near 1 AU, the present task built on the previous one by coupling semi-analytical models of MFRs with full 3-D MHD modelling of the interplanetary medium.

Before injecting any CME we needed to simulate continuously the background solar wind from the Sun to 1 AU. The particle acceleration process treated in our previous deliverable (i.e. Rouillard et al. 2025) with our shock modelling techniques made use of the Magneto-hydrodynamic Algorithm outside a Sphere (MAST) 3-D MHD coronal model (domain extending from the solar surface to $21.5 R_{\odot}$) (Lionello et al. 2009). MAST provides full 3-D simulations of the quiet corona and the accelerating solar wind. We therefore put in place a coupling pipeline capable of exploiting the MAST output at $21.5 R_{\odot}$ as input to the Heliospheric Forecasting Model (HelioCast) and the European heliospheric forecasting information asset (EUHFORIA) models.

The second step of T4.4.2 was achieved by developing two completely new modelling pipelines to propagate the MFR EFR3D and a new Spheromak model through the MAST-HelioCast background solar wind (Réville et al. 2023). We also exploited two readily available model couplings of Fri3D (Isavnin 2016; Maharana et al. 2022) and the Spheromak model (Verbeke et al. 2019) to propagate these flux ropes through the new MAST-EUHFORIA background solar wind. The four modelling pipelines developed for D4.4 (Rouillard et al. 2026) are:

- modelling the eruption and initial propagation of the MFR with the EFR3D model (Rouillard et al. 2020) from Sun to $21.5 R_{\odot}$ and then propagate the MFR through the combined MAST-HelioCast

Figure 6: The four modelling approaches investigated during D4.4 (Rouillard et al. 2026) to build the MFR propagation pipeline. Completely new couplings were put in place between the two models EFR3D and a new Spheromak MFR model with HelioCast. We also exploited two readily available model couplings based on the EUHFORIA model with Fri3D and a Spheromak (Verbeke et al. 2019) model.

background solar wind solutions **[New asset]**

- modelling the eruption and initial propagation of the MFR with a new Spheromak model from Sun to $21.5 R_{\odot}$ and then propagate the MFR through the newly combined MAST-HelioCast background solar wind solutions **[New asset]**
- modelling the eruption and initial propagation of the MFR with the Fri3D model from Sun to $21.5 R_{\odot}$ and then through the 3-D MHD EUHFORIA model (Pomoell & Poedts 2018) from $21.5 R_{\odot}$ to 1 AU. This pipeline was already developed by Maharana et al. (2022) but the novelty here was to use a new MAST-EUHFORIA model for the background solar wind **[Partially new asset]**
- modelling the eruption and initial propagation of the MFR with the Spheromak model of Verbeke et al. (2019) from Sun to $21.5 R_{\odot}$ and then through the 3-D MHD EUHFORIA model (Pomoell & Poedts 2018) from from $21.5 R_{\odot}$ to 1 AU. This pipeline was already developed by Maharana et al. (2022) but the novelty here was to use a new MAST-EUHFORIA model for the background solar wind **[Partially new asset]**

The successful completion of these technically demanding tasks provided the setup for our advanced [SEP](#) transport work. Through many considerations and comparisons we decided to retain [MAST-EUHFORIA-Fri3D](#) combination of models for the analysis of the solar and interplanetary context of [GLE74](#) detailed in the next section. On-going work will exploit the other pipelines to analyse [GLE71](#) as part of the exploitation Work Package ([WP](#))5 and included in the currently ongoing [D5.4](#).

3.2 Using the 3-D MHD [MFR](#) modelling pipeline to study [GLEs](#):

The following analysis leverages the developments described previously to assess the effect of [MFRs](#) on the transport properties of [SEPs](#). This is part of a research article stemming from [SPEARHEAD](#) that will be submitted in the coming weeks by [Rouillard et al. \(2026\)](#).

The 2024 May geomagnetic superstorm and [GLE74](#): Upon the arrival of the [CMEs](#) at Earth associated with the May geomagnetic superstorm, ground-based neutron monitors around the globe recorded a strong Forbush decrease in response to the shielding effects of these [CMEs](#) on the [GCR](#) fluxes. As the [GCR](#) fluxes reached a minimum on May 11 at 01:00 UT, [GLE74](#) was suddenly detected between 01:30 and 02:00 UT together with a powerful [SEP](#) event measured at the Lagrange L1 point and the [STEREO-A](#). These conditions were precisely those that could be addressed with our new modelling pipelines, namely a strong [SEP](#) event propagating through highly disturbed solar wind conditions and associated [MFRs](#).

We use our new modelling pipelines to study this complex sequence of events focusing on the transport of the high-energy particles inside the [CME MFRs](#) that impacted Earth. Together with advanced numerical modelling of particle transport, we could analyse the effects of these complex interplanetary conditions on the timing, spatial extent and spectral properties of high-energy [SEPs](#).

Figure 7 presents a summary of the [SEP](#) measurements by the Solar and Heliospheric Observatory (SOHO) ([Domingo et al. 1995](#)) and by the GOES/Space Environment In-Situ Suite (SEISS) ([Dichter et al. 2015](#)). As discussed in [Papaioannou et al. \(2025\)](#) relativistic protons reaching energies of approximately 500 MeV, were measured by both SOHO/EPHIN and GOES/SEISS (275–500 MeV) (see e.g. Fig. 8 of [Papaioannou et al. 2025](#)).

[GLE74](#) occurred during the geomagnetic superstorm that took place from 10–12 May 2024 and was triggered by the impact of five ejecta interacting with the Earth's magnetosphere. Figure 7 summarises the solar wind and energetic particle conditions during the geomagnetic superstorm. The sequence of ejecta that had the properties of Magnetic Obstacles ([MO](#))s was measured in-situ by the [ACE](#) and Wind spacecraft (Figure 7[e,f]). These resulted from the propagation and interaction of five [CMEs](#) launched from the Sun on 8 and 9 May. Following the sudden commencement caused by the arrival of the first interplanetary shock, the Dst index suddenly dropped to -400 nT (Figure 7[g]) and remained depressed during the entire passage of the five [MCs](#).

[Weiler et al. \(2025\)](#) modelled the propagation of these [MOs](#) using multi-spacecraft imaging, identifying their solar source regions. This enabled the solar eruptions to be unambiguously associated with their interplanetary counterparts. The study also revealed hemispheric helicity consistent with the canonical polarity rule, whereby northern-hemisphere [CMEs](#) exhibit negative helicity and southern-hemisphere [CMEs](#) exhibit positive helicity. The rapid succession of eruptions (five [CMEs](#) within ~28 hours) appeared to have impeded the normal radial expansion of the ejecta, thereby conserving elevated magnetic field intensities at L1. Despite pronounced interaction, the ejecta had not fully coalesced at L1 and distinct [MOs](#) could be discerned in the in-situ datasets from L1 and [STEREO-A](#).

Figure 7: Multi-panel overview of the 2024-05-10/11 SEP event. Panels (a)–(g) show, from top to bottom: (a) GOES soft X ray flux (green: 1–8 Å; purple: 0.5–4 Å) with flare classification thresholds indicated by dashed lines; (b) ground-based neutron monitor percent variations (DOMB, KERG, TERA, SOPB) relative the first value; (c) differential proton flux measured by GOES/SEISS for selected energy channels (legend at right); (d) differential proton flux time series across SoHO-ERNE energy bands (log scale); (e) radial component of the solar wind speed V_r , measured by Wind; (f) heliospheric magnetic field total magnitude and components (B , B_z , B_y , B_x) measured by Wind; (g) Dst index. Shaded vertical colour bands mark the six analysis intervals with the Magnetic Obstacles MO1–MO6 (labels shown inside the bottom panel); the dashed vertical lines indicate the reference times discussed in the text, including shock arrival time, flare peak intensity and onset of $>200\text{MeV}$ SEP (dashed red lines)

The arrival of the strong shock and subsequent CME MOs at Earth initially triggered a very deep Forbush decrease, as measured by the global network of neutron monitors. The onset of GLE74 occurred during the slow recovery phase (Figure 7b) and the background particle levels were already elevated due to the large SEP event of 10 May 2024 (Hayakawa et al. 2025). Comparing panels b and g in Figure 7 we can see that GLE74 began at the interface between the second and third MOs, and its peculiar proper-

ties persisted throughout the passage of the second MO. GLEs frequently occur during highly disturbed conditions at Earth due to the passage of interplanetary CMEs, suggesting complex particle transport processes between the particle accelerators on the Sun and the detectors on Earth (Masson et al. 2012; Rouillard et al. 2016).

Figure 8: View of the ecliptic plane simulated with EUHFORIA showing the MFR propagated to 1 AU. Shown in colour is the flux of SEPs propagated through the MFR using the PArticle RAdiation Asset Directed at Interplanetary Space Exploration (PARADISE) SEP transport model.

In order to study the transport effects through the third MO seen in Figure 7g, present in the interplanetary medium during GLE74, we needed to model the propagation of the associated MFR. The goal of this simulation was to capture the complexity of the interplanetary medium around the time of the GLE. Simulations of all MOs associated with the geomagnetic superstorm was beyond the scope of the analysis. Instead we focused our attention to the MO that mattered for the transport of SEPs namely the third MO.

The MAST coronal model used to reconstruct the shock's evolution was propagated beyond $21.5 R_{\odot}$ into interplanetary space using EUHFORIA model (Pomoell & Poedts 2018). Combining the MAST and EUHFORIA domains provided a continuous cube of MHD parameters from the solar surface to 1 AU and beyond. To limit the complexity of the EUHFORIA simulations, we simulated the MFR associated with MO3 and consider MO1 and MO2 as a hydrodynamic ejecta. The two CME models employed to simulate the MFR and the hydrodynamic ejecta are the Fried-3D model (Isavnin 2016) and the cone CME model (Xie et al. 2004), respectively.

The cone model comprises two components: a base circular cone and an overlying spherical frontal section (Xie et al. 2004). The base cone is described by four free parameters: the cone edge length (r), the half angular width (ω), and the latitude (λ) and longitude (φ) measured with respect to the ecliptic plane. The absence of a magnetic field in the cone model is compensated by a rise in temperature (akin to a thermal bomb) that increases locally the plasma pressure. The cone model was used to simulate the pressure induced by MO1 and MO2 on MO3. The parameters were retrieved from the The Space Weather Database Of Notifications, Knowledge, Information (DONKI), maintained at the Community Co-

ordinated Modelling Center (CCMC).

The injection of the CMEs was carried out at $21.5 R_{\odot}$ (the inner boundary of the EUHFORIA model) and propagated to 1 AU and beyond. In this way we were able to obtain a simulation of the complex magnetic fields during the impact at Earth MO3 at the time of the GLE. The pressure induced by the cone CME injected ahead of the Fried-3D flux rope produces the main shock in front of the superstorm. It also acted to limit the self-similar expansion of the Fried-3D flux rope by imposing a strong pressure ahead of the flux rope.

Figure 8 presents a snapshot of the resulting EUHFORIA simulation of the superstorm. Highlighted in the figure is the MFR of the MO3 which passed by Earth at the time of GLE74. The presence of the shock wave driven ahead of the superstorm and the different CMEs in the ecliptic plane are clearly discernible. Also shown in this figure are the results of the PARADISE model used to transport the SEP through this complex MFR. In this simulation the shock properties provided in D4.3; Rouillard et al. (2025) were used to parametrise the particle acceleration processes as input to the PARADISE model.

The rest of this detailed analysis is given in Rouillard et al. (2026) and will be incorporated in the synthesis of the scientific results, as part of WP5. It compares the observed and simulated SEP properties for this specific GLE74 event. It also contrasts the properties of SEPs that should be expected for quiet interplanetary transport and for disturbed conditions in the interplanetary medium. These were top priorities of the SPEARHEAD project, with a view to the relevant SQs.

4 Conclusions and Outlook

This deliverable has achieved the main objective of simulating the outward propagation of 3-D MFRs in support of studies of Forbush decreases as well as the transport of high-energy SEPs. Both topics are further addressed in detail as part of the scientific analysis in WP5.

Sub-task 4.4.1: exploitation of EFR3D model in combination with multi-point coronal/heliospheric imaging, we provided a semi-analytical modelling of MFRs for two events associated with strong Forbush decreases and a third very recent event in January 2026 is also under way.

Sub-task 4.4.2: the development of four modelling pipelines has allowed us to compare and contrast the advantages of different approaches. We retained a particular combination of models EUHFORIA-Fri3D-MAST to carry out a full modelling analysis of GLE74 that will be soon submitted for publication. Thanks to the combination of D4.3 (Rouillard et al. 2025) that provided the shock modelling (particle acceleration problem) and D4.4 (Rouillard et al. 2026) (particle transport problem) we are now equipped to tackle other major SEP events such as GLE71. The latter was also a case of intense SEPs propagating through a MFR to 1 AU (Rouillard et al. 2016).

The combination of D4.3 and D4.4 results provide essential input for understanding the conditions under which coronal shocks accelerate particles to very high energies and how propagating CME control the propagation of energetic particles, directly addressing all three SQs put forth by the project, namely:

- **SQ1: How are ions and electrons accelerated to the highest energies in solar eruptions?**
- **SQ2: What are the processes governing particle release from acceleration sites in the solar corona?**
- **SQ3: What are the transport conditions of ions and electrons from the Sun to 1 AU?**

Future work during the last phase of the project will focus on these fundamental science questions by extending the analysis to more GLEs.

In summary, Deliverable D4.4 (Rouillard et al. 2026) provides the modelling framework to address particle transport in the heliosphere delivering a key milestone towards the project's goals of investigating high-energy particle transport processes and thus directly facilitating SQ3.

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